

PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES ON YOUTH

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ABSTRACT

this article describes the different methods of teaching subjects. Methodological recommendations for the application of innovative technologies in the teaching of subjects in secondary schools are made. With the help of innovative technologies, it was proposed to improve the quality of lessons.

In the classroom, computer teaching is seen as a modifier and enrichment of the elements of the subject environment. At exactly such an age, students undergo a process of rapid development of the child's mental abilities, a foundation is created for the development of his or her mental potential. The use of pedagogical, innovative and information technologies in the educational process provides an opportunity to effectively solve the pressing issues of education, including :

1. on account of the fun and productivity of the learning process, the motivation of the student to perceive the material increases;
2. develops the ability to work independently and self-control;
- 3.the

effectiveness of the lesson and the assimilation of each student ensures;

4. on account of the development of thinking, perception, aspiration, imagination of each student, the overall optimal development is achieved; all children in the class are provided with active work.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The introduction of innovative and information technologies into the educational process can be characterized as a logical and necessary step in the development of the modern information world .

The rapid penetration of computers into the learning process has brought out new types, forms of teaching at an unprecedented level in the life of educators. The use of Information Technology in education is associated with the solution of two main issues: the use of computer technology in order to educate children on the use of new technical tools and to open up and improve new opportunities for students in their reading and non-reading activities. The use of Information Technology in the lessons brought a lot of problems to educators. Indeed, a modern educator should know the use of Computer, be able to use the means of computer education and be able to apply it to the educational process, constantly improve his knowledge on computer education, and hakozas are necessary. In practice, we emphasize that, for example, in the lessons of mathematics of the 3rd grade, when the teaching of instructional material was organized on the basis of computer technology, mastering significantly improved, the interest in the lesson in students increased, the ability to work independently, opportunities for mastering knowledge developed, creative approaches began to appear, confidence in himself and his knowledge began to

Especially in primary school, the organization of the course process using information communication technology is topical. Because in the 1-4 grade students developed visual-figurative thinking, it is therefore very important to organize the lesson process using computer technologies. To do this, it is necessary to prepare and use a lot of quality visual materials in a purposeful way, to introduce new views into the process of perception of knowledge, with sounds, slides,

animations. The use of ICT in various lessons in primary school provides an opportunity to move from a visual-image-narrative style of teaching to an active style, in which the student becomes an active participant, subject of the educational process. This makes it possible to assimilate knowledge in the student with understanding. Therefore, in the modern educational system, the organization of the lesson process of supporting computer technologies in the primary classes is carried out by Creative, Innovator pedagogues, which become the norm of the life work of many pedagogues . It is possible to understand through the materials of the studied science, truly, through the mathematics of the 3rd Class, the General Laws of nature and society, as well as how the knowledge of mathematical reality is of great importance to students, through simple numerical, numerical examples and corresponding explanatory texts (in the style of numbers or numbers entering the language). The process of acquiring knowledge becomes more effective when explanatory texts corresponding to the examples of recommended daily living are used in the course of classes in primary classes in the form of slides, animations, or are used independently by students in the process of extracurricular activities.

ICT is a very powerful, multifaceted, universal instrumental in the hands of the teacher, it is necessary to master it and use it purposefully in the lessons on its subject.

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the experience of organizing various classes in the primary classes of secondary schools using ICT shows that, that is, with complete confidence, the targeted use of Information

Communication Technologies creates the following opportunities:

- provides positive motivation for the learning process;
- transition of lessons at a high aesthetic and emotional level (slides, music, animations, multimedia);
- provides a high level of differentiation of teaching;
- * increases the volume of work performed in the lesson by 1.5-2 times;

* improves cognitive control;

- the educational process is organized rationally, the effectiveness of the lesson is increased;
- * the ability to search, to create is formed in the activities of the reader;
- * provides access to electronic libraries, information resources, various data systems.

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